

Rocket Nozzle Flow Control Using Proper Orthogonal Decomposition¹

David J. Lucia,² Meir Pacter,³ and Philip S. Beran⁴

Abstract

This paper investigates the use of Proper Orthogonal Decomposition-based reduced order Computational Fluid Dynamics models for model-based controller design. An open-loop optimal control problem is posed and solved concerning the regulation of a rocket engine thrust profile. The control synthesis uses a numerical flow field solver as the plant model. Controllers are synthesized using a reduced order model of the flow field generated via Proper Orthogonal Decomposition. A quasi one-dimensional supersonic convergent-divergent nozzle with varying back pressure is used as a model problem. Treating the nozzle flow as one-dimensional, the reduced order model was used to synthesize a controller that controls thrust along an ascent trajectory by varying nozzle throat area and fuel mass flow rate. The effects of reduced order model accuracy on controller performance are quantified.

1 Introduction

This paper pursues the synthesis of controllers for compressible high-speed fluid flows using reduced order Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) based models for fluid dynamics, and optimization algorithms for optimal control design. Proper Orthogonal Decomposition (POD) is a promising reduced order method for use in model based control, and some incompressible flow control applications with POD have been reported in the literature, for example see [3]. The controller synthesis strategy for a one-dimensional model problem is developed. A reduced order fluid model is developed using POD, and a sub-optimal, model-based, open-loop controller is constructed using the POD Reduced Order Model (ROM) of the plant. The performance of the POD ROM-based controller is evaluated.

¹The views expressed in this article are those of the authors and do not reflect the official position of the United States Air Force, the Department of Defense, or the U.S. Government.

²Major, USAF, Air Force Institute of Technology, WPAFB OH, 45433, david.lucia@afit.edu

³Professor, Air Force Institute of Technology, WPAFB OH, 45433, meir.pachter@afit.edu

⁴Senior Research Aerospace Engineer, Air Force Research Laboratory, WPAFB OH, 45433, philip.beran@wpafb.af.mil

2 Problem Statement

A thrust controller for a liquid fueled rocket engine with a variable throat area and adjustable propellant flow rate is considered. The rocket engine dynamics are modeled with a 1-D inviscid flow field, specifically a quasi 1-D nozzle flow. Flow control is accomplished by changing the nozzle geometry, which involves changing the nozzle throat area and the fuel mass flow rate (Figure 1). This control concept has been tested on experimental rockets[4]. The relevant parameters for

Figure 1: Variable Throat Nozzle Geometry

the chemical rocket engine were taken from the open literature[4]. The rocket engine was designed for an optimal thrust of 5000 Newtons at 25,000 meters of altitude. The rocket engine operated on a simulated ascent trajectory which entailed a linear decrease in ambient pressure over a 120 second flight time. Without any control input, the nominal thrust along this ascent trajectory increases with altitude from 3500 to 5000 Newtons. Certain launch vehicles need to restrict this increase in thrust with altitude, e.g. when launching a g-limited payload into orbit. For this model problem, an arbitrary thrust profile was selected to track with the controller.

The control problem is described as follows. The reference command signal was desired thrust T_c , and the control variables were nozzle throat area $A_c^*(t_i)$ and mass flow rate $\dot{m}(t_i)$. The states $\underline{x}(t_i)$ at time t_i are a function of the x-axis position in the nozzle \underline{X} at $n \times$ discrete locations. The output variable of interest was thrust $T(t_i)$. For a specified nozzle geometry, the system dynamics are governed by a state transition function f and initial data. The state transition

function f was obtained from the inviscid flow equations (also known as the Euler equations). Each time step required a function call to a CFD algorithm to propagate the state from one time to the next. The CFD fluid model used an explicit Roe scheme solver. The CFD flow model spatially discretized the 1-D nozzle into a grid along its length. For this problem, the state vector for the full order system had dimension $N = 750$.

3 Controller Synthesis

Perfect a priori knowledge of the ambient pressure profile was assumed along the trajectory of the rocket, and an open-loop optimal controller was pursued for this problem. Initially there were two independent control variables, throat area and propellant mass flow rate. However, the mass flow rate must be a function of throat area to maintain choked flow at the nozzle throat[2]. The considerable time scale separation allowed a myopic control synthesis. Strictly speaking, an otherwise steady flow field (time independent flow field) was disturbed by a step change in geometry (A^* and the portion of the nozzle very near the throat) at each discrete value of t_i in the open-loop simulation. The CFD code was used to perform integration in time and a new stationary (steady state) one-dimensional flow field was established. This new flow field was used to predict the thrust produced with the new A^* geometry. An easy interpolation process was used to match the calculated thrust to T_c .

4 Reduced Ordered Modeling

Reduced order modeling of the flow field was accomplished via Proper Orthogonal Decomposition. For this problem, a non-Galerkin approach was used[1]. M total snapshots (usually $O(10)$ or less) of the full order state vector length N were compiled into a $N \times M$ matrix S , known as the snapshot matrix. POD identified a reduced order mapping function Ψ to yield an optimally convergent representation of the full order variable when $\Psi = SV$. Here V is the matrix of eigenvalues of $S^T S$, and Λ is the corresponding diagonal matrix of eigenvalues. Applying this transform to the full order dynamics produced the reduced order flow solver. The POD ROM reduced the state vector dimensionality from N to M , where M was the number of snapshots.

5 Results

A reduced order model was generated from four snapshots of the full order system state vector, taken at

even intervals as the flow solver progressed from initial condition to steady state. The snapshots were obtained from the full order flow solver explicit time integration with the nozzle geometry required at 20 seconds into the flight trajectory (approximate). These four snapshots produced a reduced order model with four modes for each of the three conserved flow variables. This resulted in a total state dimensionality of twelve. The twelve modes were applied to the unsteady equations and time integrated to steady state.

Figure 2: Sub-Optimal Thrust Performance

The reduced order plant was inserted into the optimization algorithm, and the algorithm was run to generate a sub-optimal controller. The sub-optimal controller thrust performance, based on the full order plant, is shown in Figure 2. The optimization algorithm, based on the reduced order plant, introduced a slowly growing error in thrust. When necessary, reduced order model accuracy can be adjusted to achieve desired performance goals by varying the number of modes and dispersion of snapshots[1]. The mean error for this sub-optimal controller was $21.8N$ which is a 0.43% error.

References

- [1] P. S. Beran, L. J. Huttsell, B. J. Buxton, C. Noll, and G. Osswald. Computational aeroelastic techniques for viscous flow. In *CEAS/AIAA/ICASE/NASA Langley International Forum on Aeroelasticity and Structural Dynamics*, Williamsburg, VA, June 22-25, 1999.
- [2] P.G. Hill and C.R. Peterson. *Mechanics and Thermodynamics of Propulsion*. Addison-Wesley Publishing Company, 1965.
- [3] K. Ito and S. S. Ravindran. A reduced-order method for simulation and control of fluid flows. *Journal of Computational Physics*, 143:403-425, 1998.
- [4] G.P. Sutton. *Rocket Propulsion Elements*. John Wiley and Sons, 1992.